
**Socio-Economic Status Of Working Women In Satara City
(Maharashtra)**

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Abstract:

This study examines the socio-economic status (SES) of working women in Satara city, Maharashtra, focusing on three distinct occupational sectors: household industry, other unorganized sectors, and organized sectors. Using primary data collected from 150 respondents through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using the Kuppaswamy SES classification model, the study highlights disparities in women's socio-economic conditions. The findings reveal that women employed in organized sectors predominantly belong to upper middle and upper classes, with higher education, income, and better access to resources. Conversely, women working in household industries and unorganized sectors largely fall within the lower middle class, reflecting limited access to education, healthcare, and financial opportunities. The study also explores the influence of caste, religion, and educational attainment on occupational placement, showing that women from marginalized communities are overrepresented in low-skill, low-income occupations. Income levels were strongly correlated with SES, indicating that women from higher SES backgrounds earn significantly more and tend to work in organized sectors, driven by career aspirations and economic independence. In contrast, women from lower SES groups often work out of necessity to meet basic family needs. The research underscores the need for targeted interventions to enhance educational and employment opportunities for women in unorganized sectors, aiming to reduce socio-economic disparities and promote equitable development.

Keywords: *Socio-Economic Status (SES), Upper Lower Class (ULC), Upper Lower Class (ULC), Upper Middle Class (UMC), Upper Class (UC).*

Introduction:

Number of working women is increasing day by day in modern era especially in urban region due to education, employment opportunities, and reservation policies by government, increasing needs of herself and her family, responsibilities, and also awareness about career and future. However, their

participation is huge in unorganized sector of occupation. Women in Satara city also have same condition. Without equal access to the job market, women cannot participate in better-paid work so their economic status remains stunted (Meena Razvi, Nene L. Roth, 2004). Socio-economic indicators play important role for studying status of individuals. Women

are suffering different problems due to patriarchy social system, even they are working in different occupational sectors. Hence their socio-economic status also affected by traditions and taboos of society. They are suffering double burden of work at home and work place and adding to this they are suffering occupational diseases and hazards, exploitation and harassment at workplace, gender biasness at workplace which is not faced by general women.

According to United Nations (1997), “women are the invisible workforce in India” Women in different occupational sectors have different socio-economic status because it is impact of education, her income, family’s income, occupation, health, religion, caste, marital status etc. Vecchio and Roy argued that education in India is sex and class discriminatory (Meena Razvi, Nene L. Roth, 2004). There is close relationship between caste and occupation because according to report on conditions of work and promotion of livelihood in unorganized sector (2007), females of lower caste engaged mostly in low status unorganized occupations. In Satara city females are mostly working in household industry and other unorganized sectors. Hence females of these sectors selected for study and compared to females of organized sector.

Study Region:

Satara District locates at the Western limit of the Deccan plateau with hilly reliefs in southern of Maharashtra state. Extreme Western part of the district
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falls under Sahyadri ranges. The studied geographical area is the Satara City, which is situated around the latitude 17.69 N and longitude 74.00 E. It is surrounded by seven hills. This area is important for analysis because it is large city in Satara district and have high concentration of population with different socio-economic status and central government activities which means that the impact of inequality with respect to socio-economic status of women occurs in different occupations.

Objectives:

1. To study socio-economic status of working women in different occupational background.
2. To compare socio-economic status of working women in different occupational background.

Research Methodology:

The present study is studied socio-economic status of women workers in various occupations of Satara city. This study is based on Primary and secondary data. Primary data is collected through questionnaire. Simple random sampling method is used ensuring the representativeness of sample. In this study 150 samples are selected from workers of household industry, other unorganized sectors except agricultural sector and organized sector. 50 samples are selected from each sector. Kuppuswamy model for classification of socio-economic status is applied. Then percentile method is used for comparison. Secondary data is collected through, Census, reports, journals, articles, websites etc.

Results and Discussions:**Table No. 1 Distribution Female workers by occupation:**

Sr. No.	Type of Occupation	Male (%)	Female (%)
1.	Agricultural Workers	0.65	1.47
2.	Household Industry	3.06	8.24
3.	Other	94.75	88.76

Source: Census 2011, Satara District

The above table indicates that female's participation in agricultural sector (1.47 %) is higher than male (0.65 %) but lowest as compared to other sectors. It is impact of urbanization. In household industry, female's participation is also low i.e. 8.24% and other sectors indicates highest participation of male and female i.e. 94.75% and 88.76% respectively. However, female's participation in this

workforce is lower than male. According to report on conditions of work and promotion of livelihood in unorganized sector (2007), females are hugely engaged in unorganized and unskilled job. Hence, male's participation is highest in other activities. Because organized sector, professional occupations, skilled occupations included in this strata.

Table No. 2 Socio-economic Status scaling of working women:

Sr. No.	SES	Household Industry (%)	Other Unorganized Sectors (%)	Organized Sector (%)
1.	Upper Lower Class	4	4	0
2.	Lower Middle Class	62	56	6
3.	Upper Middle Class	34	40	72
4.	Upper Class	0	0	22
5.	Total	100	100	100

Source: Field Survey

Kuppaswamy model for classification of SES is applied and results are presented in above table. Working women of selected sectors found in 4 classes such as upper lower class, lower middle class, upper middle class and upper class. According to data in above table, in household industry, most of females are living in lower middle class i. e. 62%. Upper middle class shows 34 % females share where and 4% females comes under

upper lower class whereas no one found in upper class. Socio-economic status in other unorganized sector reveals that most of women of this field also are living in upper middle class (56%) followed by 40% of upper middle class and 4% of upper lower class. There is absence in upper class.

In organized Sector, Most of women are living in upper middle class which shows 72% share, 22% are in upper

class. Very low percentage i.e. 6% are in lower class.
lower middle class. No one found in upper

Table No. 3 Socio-economic Status and Religion:

Sr. No.	SES		Household Industry (%)				Other unorganized Sector(%)				Organized Sector (%)				
			H	B	M	O	H	B	M	O	H	B	M	O	
1.	Upper Class	Lower Class	100	-	-	-	50	50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	Lower Class	Middle Class	90.32	9.68	-	-	75.00	7.15	14.26	3.58	1.33	-	1.33	1.33	-
3.	Upper Class	Middle Class	88.24	5.88	5.88	-	80	10	10	-	81.82	9.09	9.09	-	-
4.	Upper Class		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	83.33	11.11	5.56	-	-

Source: Field Survey

The data presented in the above table indicate that percentage of female belongs to Hindu religion is higher belongs to all class in all three sectors except upper lower class of other unorganized sector. Contribution of Hindu females is highest in household industry belongs to upper lower class i.e. (100%) and lowest (1.33%) in organized sector belongs to also lower middle class. Baudhh females contribution is highest in other unorganized sector belongs to upper lower class (50%) and lowest in organized

sector belongs to lower middle class (0%). Other unorganized sector included low skill or unskilled population. Muslim Women's contribution is highest in other unorganized sector and they belongs to lower middle class. Muslim women from upper lower class are not presented in all three sectors. Other religion's presentation is very tiny. Their presentation observed only in house hold industry and organized sector belongs to lower middle class i. e. 3.58% and 1.33% respectively.

Table No. 4 Socio-economic status and Caste

Sr. No.	SES	Household Industry (%)					Other unorganized Sector(%)					Organized Sector (%)				
		Open	OBC	SC	ST	NT	Open	OBC	SC	ST	NT	Open	OBC	SC	ST	NT
1.	ULC	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	50	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	LMC	51.62	29.02	9.68	-	9.68	42.85	25	17.85	7.15	7.15	3.33	3.33	-	-	3.33
3.	UMC	64.70	17.65	17.65	-	-	54.55	45.45	-	-	-	54.55	45.45	-	-	-
4.	UpC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	52.78	19.45	13.889	8.33	5.55

Source: Field Survey

It could be observed from the above data that working women of open category who are working in household industry tend to be from upper lower class which is highest representation of them. Their lowest representation seen in organized sector who came from lower middle class. Working women of OBC category presented highest contribution in other unorganized sector and organized sector belongs to upper middle class i.e. 45.45 % while lowest in organized sector belongs to lower middle class. Working women of SC category are working in other unorganized sector in large quantity belonging upper lower class (50%). In household industry, they are from lower

middle class having 29.02% representation and lowest in upper middle class (17.65 %). There is absence of ST female workers in household industry belongs to all class. In organized sector they are presenting only from upper class. However it is little (8.33 %) as compared to other categories except NT. Their large share (50%) is found in other unorganized sector who are indicating upper lower class. Contribution of working women of NT category in obtained in household industry belongs to lower middle class (9.68 %), in other unorganized sector belongs to same class (7.15%) and in organized sector belongs to upper class (5.55 %).

Table No. 5 Socio-economic status and Educational Level

Sr. No.	SES	Household Industry (%)						Other unorganized Sector(%)						Organized Sector (%)				
		P.G	U.G	HS	S	P	I	PG	U.G	HS	S	P	I	P.G	U.G	HS	S	D
1.	ULC	-	50	50		-	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	LMC	-	6.45	51.62	35.48	-	6.45	-	78.57	21.43	-	-	-			33.33	66.67	-
3.	UMC	5.88	5.88	17.65	47.05	23.54	5.88	-	40	-	45	10	5	27.28	45.45	-	9.09	18.18
4.	UpC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5.48	27.78	2.78	11.11	2.78

Source: Field Survey

The data presented in above table reveals that all the respondents who obtained post-graduation are related to higher socio-economic status i.e. 27.2% from upper middle class and 5.48% from Upper class. They are representing in organized sector. Post graduated working women are not working in household industry and other unorganized sector. However working women belongs to upper middle class in

household industry (5.88%) acquired post-graduation educational level. 6.45 % and 5.88% working women belongs to lower middle class and upper middle class respectively in household industry who are illiterate. Working women who obtained under graduation (78.75 %) belongs to lower middle class representing in other unorganized sector which is largest proportion of working women in all

sectors belongs to all class. Working women related to upper lower class are acquired higher secondary level and

presenting in other unorganized sector.

Table No. 6 Socio-economic status and Monthly Income (in 000 Rs.)

Sr. No.	SES	Household Industry (%)				Other unorganized Sector(%)				Organized Sector (%)			
		10>	10-20	20-30	30<	10>	10-20	20-30	30<	10>	10-20	20-30	30<
1.	ULC	-	100	-	-	50	50	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	LMC	-	70.97	29.03	-	57.14	32.14	10.72	-	100	-	-	-
3.	UMC	52.94	47.06	-	-	35	50	5	10	36.36	-	45.46	18.18
4.	Up C	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5.55	-	52.78	41.66

Source: Field Survey

Above table reveals that in household industry, most of working women's (100%) earned income ranges between below 10000 who are belonging lower middle class. In household industry, working women's income is below 20000 Rs per month of all socio-economic background. Only 29.03% women from lower middle class in this sector earned 20000 to 30000 Rs. per month. In other unorganized sector, women from upper lower class earn below 20000 Rs per month, from lower middle class i.e below 30000 and from upper middle class, only 10% women's monthly income is above 30000 Rs. 100% females from lower middle class earn below 10000 Rs. per month in organized sector. In organized sector 45.46% women from upper middle class earn between 20000 to 30000Rs per month and only 18.18 % women's income is above 30000 Rs. per month. In this sector, monthly income of 52.78 % women from upper class is ranging between 20000 to 30000 Rs. per month and 41.66%

women from upper class is above 30000 Rs.

Conclusion:

Women who are working in organized sector are living in high socio-economic status while women workers of household industry and other organized sectors are presenting low socio-economic status as compared to organized sector. High percentage in lower middle class in these sectors indicates females of these sectors are living with less access to financial, educational, social and health services. According to study, it mean to say that Bauddh women from upper lower class forced into occupations of other unorganized sector for subsistence. Representation of working women of open category in all sectors with all class is highest as compared to their counterparts. Working Women belongs to upper class are working only in organized sector. It mean to say that higher socio- economic status of family causes occupational status of women. This study reveals that most of

working women of ST and ST category belongs to lower class are working in other unorganized where advance skill or technical knowledge is not required. Mostly, working women who obtained post- graduation level are working in organized sector belonging upper middle class and upper class. Illiterate working women are working in household industry and unorganized sector who belongs to lower middle and upper middle class. Working women who obtained degree of diploma are observed in organized sector belonging upper middle class and upper class. It means, working women with high educational and with high socio-economic status are working in organized sector which enhance their individual socio-economic status.

In this study, it is concluded that individual monthly income of females is high who are belonging high socio-economic status while low who are belonging low socio-economic status. Finally, it does mean to say that women with upper class background family have high education and also individual income and highly working in organized sector where as women with lower class background family have low educational status and individual income. As per field survey, most of working women belongs to high socio-economic status are working for career ambition, economic independency, better standard of living,

respect, security of future etc. On the contrast, working women belongs to low socio-economic status are working for indispensable needs, economic problems in family, responsibility of children etc.

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